

Investor's Behaviour towards Retail Investment in Stock Market – A Study in Rajamahendravaram, AP

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Abstract: Retail investors are now interested in the stock market as a place to invest their money, and the market has grown significantly over the years. But many people are afraid to put money into the stock market because of the market's volatility. Investors in the stock market often take on a lot of risks, and they fear losing their hard-earned money. Even though investors get a lot of money back from the stock market, they also must take on many risks. They also have to be sure which investment path they choose to make sure they get a lot of money back. But in India, more and more people are putting their hard-earned money into equity. In this situation, the present study looks at how investors in the East Godavari district feel about the stock market. It is in this context, present study was undertaken with these objectives: i) to know the demographic and investment profile of sample investors; ii) to study the influence of demographic profiles on behavioural biases and iii) to analyse the influence of investment profile on behavioural biases. The study was carried out with the support of primary data. Data were collected by using a structured questionnaire and were processed both manually and also with the help of computer software like Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) 24 version. The data was collected from Rajahmundry city (AP) using the purposive sampling method and snowball sampling method. The sample size for the study was only 110. After analysing the primary data collected and it is found that i) there is a difference between the demographic profile of the investor and behavioural biases and ii) there is a difference between the investment profile of the investor and behavioural biases.

Keywords: Investor's behaviour, Investment, Risk, Stock market, Volatility.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is very essential to know what attracts the retail investors towards equities despite its constant volatility. Another important question is that on whom they depend when parting with their funds, how they dissect the information obtained from various sources and then take a decision. Thus this study on retail investors behaviour towards equity investment in the stock market becomes essential in analysing the mindset of the investors, pre and post their investment in the stock market. Interacting with investors is not only about giving them information but also enlightening them about the risks involved by investing in equities which may not have strong fundamentals. There are number of investment avenues that investors can choose to invest in. With several investment avenues available it is always beneficial to diversify ones portfolio depending on their investment requirements. To get the best out of investment, an understanding of human nature in financing perspective is required. The point of distinction between investors' investing behaviour includes factors like demographic factors which includes socio-economic background, educational attainment level, age, race and sex. The investment before was found to be significant influencing factor of overall investment behaviour of the investors (Sumandiran Prithiviraj, Gokul, 2018).

Elements of Investment

Retail Investors: A non-professional investor that buys and sells securities or funds that hold a basket of assets, such as mutual funds and exchange-traded funds, is referred to as a retail investor. This kind of investor is also known as an individual investor (ETF). Trades made by retail investors may be executed via either conventional or online brokerage companies or through several alternative forms of investment accounts. Retail

investors often trade far lower sums than institutional investors, acquiring assets for their accounts rather than a company's accounts. The phrase "institutional investor" refers to larger-scale investments made by professional portfolio and fund managers, such as those who may manage a pension fund or a mutual fund.

Retail Investment: As per SEBI, an individual retail investor is an investor who applies or bids for securities or a value of not more than Rs 2,00,000 in an initial public offering (IPO), and an investor who buys or holds shares worth less than Rs 2,00,000 in a stock. Retail individual investors cannot apply or bid for securities valued at more than Rs 2,00,000. Regarding commodities, no such restriction can be used to identify a retail investor.

Stock Market: The Indian stock market is one of the oldest and largest in the world. The country's fast modernisation since gaining independence must invest to use money with the expectation of a future financial return or growth in value. Everyone is interested in investing regardless of their background, income level, or social standing. Financial planners and the government are concerned with ensuring everyone can invest and earn returns on their unused resources to generate a certain amount of money for a particular purpose in life and provide for the stock market's uncertain future vitality.

An investigation into the behaviour of individuals who invest in the stock market in the East Godavari district will be the focus of the present study. Only investors from the East Godavari district were considered for inclusion in the study because of its objective. The research was conducted using the perspective of investors considering investors in the stock market. The research will be useful in gaining a better understanding of investments in the stock market, which will, in turn, aid with making sound choices in the market. In addition to helping them make a decent profit, the different aspects that need to be considered could be utilised to mitigate the market risk associated with their investments. Because the predictions for the market certainly shift numerous times, it is impossible to determine the return with precision. This study may assist the individual investor and will be of great benefit, providing important information at the time of investment in the stock market.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The expansion of the financial industry in India has made it possible for individuals to take advantage of investment possibilities. Countries such as Singapore have seen an increase in the frequency of investment, which has contributed to the stock market's rapid expansion (Rao, 2018). An investigation of the fundamental factors that play a role in the decisions made by individual equity investors with significant holdings in fortune 500 companies has been carried out in the form of a survey. The criteria for wealth maximisation were found to be significant among investors; however, the influence of suggestions made by brokerage companies, individual stockbrokers, family members, and co-workers was insignificant (Nagy & Bamberger, 1994). The demographic and psychographic characteristics were effective on the risk-bearing ability of Indian investors by performing a sampling survey. Evaluating the acquired data by multinomial logistic regression and factor analysis (FA) of SPSS showed a strong relationship between risk-taking attitude and demographic and psychographic characteristics (Kiran & Rao, 2005).

The underlying cause that influences the behaviour of individual investors is planned behaviour. The researchers obtained the information by distributing a questionnaire to the individuals living in the city of Coimbatore, located in the state of Tamil Nadu in India. They conducted regression analysis and discovered that

social variables, including social contacts and the media, changed individual investors' trading behaviour (Shanmugham & Ramya, 2012). To investigate the impact that demographic factors have on decision-making about investments, a sample survey was carried out in Chennai, India. According to the findings of the research, changes in demographic parameters such as age, income, education, and occupation had an impact on the preference of investment avenues on the part of the investors. These aspects were considered from the investors' perspective (Geetha & Vimala, 2014). It was discovered that male investors had a better degree of awareness about the various investment opportunities than female investors. Furthermore, female investors showed less confidence in their investment selections, resulting in lower satisfaction levels (Arti et al., 2011). It has been shown that factors such as profitability, tax aversion, prospects, the worth of money over time, and other similar factors encourage a retail investor to buy gold as an investment (Hundal et al., 2013). Married women were more likely to invest their money in stocks, mutual funds, insurance, and fixed deposits than younger single women or never married (Sellappan et al., 2013).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Investment choices are significantly influenced by psychological and behavioural factors rather than merely a simple examination of facts and figures. It is a well-known fact that people's ability to make complex decisions is limited and susceptible to emotional and mental influences. Investors' willingness to take risks. The investigation of investors' expectations about Investors has shown more human characteristics, such as anxiety, risk-seeking and aversion, colleagues' suggestions, and enjoyment, when making investment decisions, as opposed to a more systematic approach. is one factor in finding their character. Several aspects of this issue have been voiced by investors in the targeted region of Rajahmundry. These implications have been specifically examined regarding stock market knowledge across a variety of dimensions, variables influencing investment choices, and investor satisfaction levels. It is obvious that every one of them is relevant to the research area because they each have an impact on how investors see the dimension.

3. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the study is to realise the following:

1. To know the demographic and investment profile of sample investors.
2. To study the influence of demographic profiles on behavioural biases.
3. To analyse the influence of investment profile on behavioural biases.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sample Design: The data was collected from Rajahmundry city using the purposive sampling method and snowball sampling method. The sample size for the study was only 110.

Data and Analysis: The study was carried out with the support of primary data. Data were collected by using a structured questionnaire. The collected data were processed both manually and also with the help of computer software like Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) 24 version. Frequency analysis, Reliability statistics, Rank correlation, ANOVA, t-test, and regression analysis were used in the study.

Scope and period: The primary data were collected through a field survey, using the google form link share on social media, from June 2022 to August 2022.

Hypotheses of the study: The following hypothesis were developed in tune with the above study objectives.

1. *There is no difference between the demographic profile of the investor and behavioural biases (H_{0A}).*
2. *There is no difference between the investment profile of the investor and behavioural biases (H_{0B}).*

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, an attempt has been made to present the study analysis and discussion. Suitable statistical techniques were used to find out the relationship between demographic profiles and behavioural biases. As the data belongs primary in nature, it is necessary to do a reliability analysis to check whether the data is worthy to carry out the study. The results are shown in the following table.

Table – 1: Reliability statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
0.864	09

Source: Primary data, computed using SPSS 23

The above table presents the result of the reliability of the data. It was conducted to assess the consistency of the questionnaire, and it recorded relatively high internal consistency. Hence, the instrument was fit to analyse the collected data. The analysis of the demographic profile of the investors is presented in the following table given below. The demographic profile of the investors showed been given in terms of age, marital status, education, area, occupation, family members, income, gender, and willingness to invest in equity.

Demographic profiles of the investors: In the gender-wise distribution, the majority (76.36%) were males. In the age category, the majority (48.18%) of the investors belonged to the age group of 20-30 years. In terms of marital status, the majority were married, 73(66.36%). In education qualification, the majority of investors were postgraduates 49(44.55%). In the residential area category, majorities were from the urban area 81(73.64%). Regarding occupation level, majorities were working in the government sector 32 (29.09). Regarding total family members, a majority of 76 (69.09%) were in 3-5 categories. In income level, the majority of investors (61) earned an income between 20001 – 30000. With reference to investment in equity, 19 (17.27%) investors were not willing to invest in equity shares, and 91 (2.73%) investors were willing to invest in equity.

Table – 2: Demographic profile of the investors

Variables	Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Below 20	7	6.36%
	20-30	53	48.18%
	31-40	21	19.09%
	41-50	18	16.36%
	Above 50	11	10.00%
Marital Status	Married	73	66.36%
	Unmarried	37	33.64%
Education	Higher Secondary	18	16.36%
	Graduate	24	21.82%
	Postgraduate	49	44.55%

	Professional	19	17.27%
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Area	Urban	81	73.64%
	Rural	29	26.36%
Occupation	Government	32	29.09%
	Private	29	26.36%
	Family Business	16	14.55%
	Retired	12	10.91%
	Housewife	21	19.09%
Family Members	Below 3	11	10.00%
	03 - 05	76	69.09%
	05 - 07	14	12.73%
	Above 7	9	8.18%
Income	Below 20000	25	22.73%
	20001 - 30000	61	55.45%
	30001- 40000	11	10.00%
	40001 - 50000	6	5.45%
	Above 50000	7	6.36%
Willing invest in equity	Yes	91	82.73%
	No	19	17.27%
Gender	Male	84	76.36%
	Female	26	23.64%
	Total	110	100.00%

Source: Primary data

Classification of investors based on equity investment: Table – 3 presents the frequency analysis for the investment profile of the investors, the investment profile of the investors indicated a preference for equity investment and 48 investors (43.64%) saved 10 to 20 per cent from their income for equity investment. The majority of investors, 49 (44.55%), reported 05 – 10 years of experience in investing.

Table – 3: Classification of investors based on equity investment

Variables	Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Percentage of Savings	Up to 10	34	30.91%
	11 - 20	48	43.64%
	21 - 30	13	11.82%
	31 - 40	15	13.64%
	Total	110	100.00%
Years of Investing	Less than 5 years	32	29.09%
	05 - 10	49	44.55%
	11 - 20	16	14.55%
	21 - 30	11	10.00%
	More than 30 years	2	1.82%
	Total	110	100.00%

Source: Primary data, computed using SPSS 24

Hypothesis testing: A hypothesis was performed to find the statistical significance of the study objectives. In the present study, the researcher is confined to testing the specific behavioural biases, namely the overconfidence of the investors.

H01: There is no difference between the gender of the investors and behavioural biases (H_{0A1}).

Table– 4: Difference between males and females with respect to investor behavioural biases (H_{0A1})

Overconfidence		Mean	SD	t - Value	P - Value	Decision
Gender	Male	4.07	0.42	109.56	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
	Female	4.06	0.36			

Source: Primary data

For analyzing, t-test was performed to find the difference between males and females with respect to investor behavioural biases. The p-value is less than 0.05 for a behavioural factor of overconfidence; it leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It indicates that there is a significant difference in opinion between males and females with respect to investor behavioural biases (overconfidence).

H02: There is no difference between the age of the investor and behavioural biases (H_{0A2}).

Table – 5: Difference among age groups (year) regarding investor behavioural biases (H_{0A2})

Overconfidence		Mean	SD	F - Value	P - Value	Decision
Age group (in years)	Up to 20	3.65	0.39	0.26	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
	21-30	4.04	0.42			
	31-40	4.07	0.39			
	41-50	4.08	0.44			
	Above 50	4.01	0.41			

Source: Primary data

ANOVA test was performed to find the difference among the age group of the investors toward investor behavioural biases. The p-value is less than 0.05 for the behavioural factor of overconfidence, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It indicates that there is a significant difference in opinion among the age group of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (overconfidence). Overconfidence of the investors varies based on the investor age group.

H03: There is no difference between the marital status of the respondent and investor and behavioural biases (H_{0A3}).

Table – 6: Difference between marital status of the investor with respect to investor behavioural biases (H_{0A3})

Overconfidence		Mean	SD	t - Value	P - Value	Decision
Marital Status	Married	4.01	0.29	127.21	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
	Unmarried	3.46	0.44			

Source: Primary data

For analyzing, t-test was performed to find the difference between the marital status of the investors with respect to behavioural biases. The p-value is less than 0.05 for the behavioural factor of overconfidence, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It indicates that there is a significant difference in opinion due to the marital status of the investors regarding the overconfidence of the investor while investing.

H04: There is no difference between the educational qualifications of the investor and behavioural biases (H_{0A4}).

Table – 7: Difference among educational qualifications of investors towards investor behavioural biases (H_{0A4})

Overconfidence		Mean	S D	χ^2 - Value	P - Value	Decision
Educational qualifications	Intermediate	3.54	0.35	194.64	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
	Graduate	3.69	0.41			
	Postgraduate	3.63	0.38			
	Professional	3.65	0.37			

Source: Primary data

A Chi-Square test was performed to find the difference in opinion among educational qualifications of the investors towards investor behavioural biases. The p-value is less than 0.05 for the behavioural factor of overconfidence, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It indicates that there is a significant difference in opinion among educational qualifications of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (overconfidence).

H05: There is no difference between the area of the respondent and investor and behavioural biases (H_{05}).

Table – 8: - Difference between the area of the investors with respect to investor behavioural biases (H_{0A5})

Overconfidence		Mean	SD	t Value	P Value	Decision
Area	Urban	4.01	0.31	114.23	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
	Rural	3.28	0.39			

Source: Primary data

For analyzing, t-test was performed to find the difference between the area of the investors with respect to investor behavioural biases. The p-value is less than 0.05 for the behavioural factor of overconfidence, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It indicates that there is a significant difference between the area of the investors with respect to investor behavioural biases (overconfidence).

H06: There is no difference between the occupation of the investors and behavioural biases (H_{0A6}).

Table – 9: Difference among occupation of investors towards investor behavioural biases (H_{0A6})

Overconfidence		Me an	SD	χ^2 - Value	P - Value	Decision
Occupation	Government	3.63	0.38	175.82	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
	Private	3.66	0.31			
	Business	3.63	0.39			
	Professional	3.71	0.36			

Source: Primary data

A Chi-Square test was performed to find the difference in opinion among occupations of the investors towards investor behavioural biases. The p-value is less than 0.05 for the behavioural factor of overconfidence, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It indicates that there is a significant difference in opinion among occupation of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (overconfidence).

H07: There is no difference between the family size of the respondent and investor and behavioural biases (H_{0A7}).

Table – 10: Difference among the family size of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (H_{0A7})

Overconfidence		Mean	SD	F - Value	P - Value	Decision
Family size	Below 3	3.63	0.38	4.19	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
	03 - 05	3.67	0.39			
	05 - 07	3.77	0.32			
	Above 7	3.63	0.44			

Source: Primary data

ANOVA test was performed to find the difference in the family size of the investors towards investor behavioural biases. The p-value is less than 0.05 for the behavioural factor of overconfidence, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It indicates that there is a significant difference in opinion among the family size of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (overconfidence).

H08: There is no difference between the monthly income of the investor and behavioural biases (H_{0A8}).

Table – 11: Difference among the monthly income of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (H_{0A8})

Overconfidence		Me an	SD	F - Value	P - Value	Decision
Monthly income (Rs.)	up to 20000	3.66	0.39	0.53	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
	20000 - 30000	3.61	0.41			
	30000 - 40000	3.65	0.37			
	above 40000	3.62	0.40			

Source: Primary data

ANOVA test was performed to find the difference in the monthly income of the investors towards investor behavioural biases. The p-value is less than 0.05 for the behavioural factor of overconfidence, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It indicates that there is a

significant difference in opinion among the monthly income of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (overconfidence).

HYPOTHESIS TESTING OF THE INVESTMENT PATTERN OF THE INVESTORS

H09: There is no difference between the percentage of savings of the investor and behavioural biases (H_{0B1}).

Table – 12: Difference among the percentage of savings of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (H_{0B1})

Overconfidence		Mean	SD	F Value	P Value	Decision
Percentage of savings (Rs)	up to 10	4.11	0.43	0.68	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
	11 - 20	4.12	0.51			
	21 - 30	4.12	0.43			
	31 - 40	4.09	0.43			

Source: Primary data

ANOVA test was performed to find the difference in the percentage of savings of the investors towards investor behavioural biases. The p-value is less than 0.05 for the behavioural factor of overconfidence, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It indicates that there is a significant difference in opinion among the percentage of the savings of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (overconfidence).

H010: There is no difference between the investment period of the investor and behavioural biases (H_{0B2}).

Table-13: Difference among the period of the investment of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (H_{0B2})

Overconfidence		Mean	SD	F Value	P Value	Decision
Period of investment (in years)	< 5	3.93	0.39	0.94	0.000	Reject Null Hypothesis
	05 - 10	3.95	0.49			
	11 - 20	3.98	0.38			
	21 - 30	3.97	0.40			
	> 30	4.00	0.39			

Source: Primary data

ANOVA test was performed to find the difference among the period of investment of the investors towards investor behavioural biases. The p-value is less than 0.05 for the behavioural factor of overconfidence, which leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It indicates that there is a significant difference in opinion among the period of investment of the investors towards investor behavioural biases (overconfidence).

Table-14: Summary of Results

Sl.No.	NULL HYPOTHESES	RESULTS
1	There is no difference between the gender of the investors and behavioural biases	Rejected
2	There is no difference between the age of the investor and behavioural biases	Rejected
3	There is no difference between the marital status of the respondent and investor and behavioural	Rejected

	biases	
4	There is no difference between the educational qualifications of the investor and behavioural biases	Rejected
5	There is no difference between the area of the respondent and investor and behavioural biases	Rejected
6	There is no difference between the occupation of the investors and behavioural biases	Rejected
7	There is no difference between the family size of the respondent and investor and behavioural biases	Rejected
8	There is no difference between the monthly income of the investor and behavioural biases	Rejected
9	There is no difference between the percentage of savings of the investor and behavioural biases	Rejected
10	There is no difference between the investment period of the investor and behavioural biases	Rejected

6. CONCLUSION

When it comes to investing, overconfidence bias often causes people to overestimate how much they know about financial markets or particular assets, leading them to ignore evidence as well as the advice of experts. This frequently leads to individuals making improper attempts to time the market or developing concentrations in high-risk assets that they think to be safe. The emotion of investors or their confidence may drive the market to move up or down, which in turn can influence the price of stocks to go up or down. A dynamic stock market in which stock prices are rising and investor confidence is expanding is an example of a bull market or vice versa. An attempt is made to study the behavioural biases of the investor and whether overconfidence has an impact on the investor's decision. The study reveals that the investor's overconfidence has an impact when taking an investment decision. The overconfidence bias has an effect and varies on the demographic variables like age, occupation, income, marital status, education, gender etc., of the investors.

The study was based on primary data collected from selected individual investors, and it was done to gain a deeper understanding of the attitude of the investors in the equity investment (stock market). The screen-based trading system, establishment of depositories and dematerialisation, rolling and settlement, derivatives trading, and others were significant development in the stock market in modern times. It has resulted in better transparency in dealings, improvement in market infrastructure and ease of operation and quick settlement of transactions. The current study analyses the attitude of investors in the various forms of dimensions as awareness, factors influencing investment decisions, intention to invest and satisfaction were analysed. The majority of the investors were well-known that equity is a risky investment. Income and awareness levels have highly influenced the intention to invest.

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